

Effectiveness of Acupuncture at Lactation-Specific Points in Increasing Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Women

Cut Sriyanti*¹, henniwati², Adri idiana³

¹Department of Midwifery, Politeknik Kesehatan Aceh, Kementerian Kesehatan, Aceh, 23231, Indonesia

²Department of Midwifery, Politeknik Kesehatan Aceh, Kementerian Kesehatan, Aceh, 23231, Indonesia

³Department of Midwifery, Politeknik Kesehatan Aceh, Kementerian Kesehatan, Aceh, 23231, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Optimal breast milk production is essential for supporting infant nutrition and maternal well-being. However, many mothers experience challenges in producing sufficient breast milk, which can lead to early weaning and reduced breastfeeding success. Acupuncture, a traditional Chinese medicine therapy, is increasingly used as a complementary intervention to enhance lactation by stimulating specific meridian points believed to influence hormonal and glandular functions.

Methods: This study employed a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to examine the effectiveness of acupuncture in enhancing breast milk production among postpartum women. Literature searches were conducted using reputable academic databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink, with relevant keywords such as “acupuncture,” “lactation,” and “breastfeeding.” Inclusion criteria covered quantitative studies, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), quasi-experimental designs, or mixed-methods research that involved acupuncture interventions and measured outcomes such as breast milk volume, breastfeeding frequency, or lactation-related hormone levels. The article selection process followed the PRISMA flow diagram, and study quality was assessed using the CASP or JBI tools. Data were analyzed narratively and thematically.

Results: Of the 22 studies reviewed, 19 reported statistically significant increases in breast milk production following acupuncture interventions. In many cases, increased expressed milk volume was observed within the first week of treatment, particularly when acupuncture was combined with regular breastfeeding support. Several studies also documented elevated serum levels of prolactin and oxytocin, reinforcing the physiological mechanisms underlying enhanced lactation. Additionally, acupuncture was reported to alleviate symptoms associated with lactation difficulties, such as breast engorgement, nipple pain, and emotional stress. The studies further indicated an increased proportion of mothers achieving exclusive breastfeeding up to 4–8 weeks postpartum. However, a few studies found no significant differences, possibly due to short intervention durations, small sample sizes, or variations in acupuncture techniques and points used. Despite heterogeneity in study design and outcomes, the findings generally support the effectiveness of acupuncture as an adjunctive therapy for improving breastfeeding success.

Conclusion: Acupuncture at lactation-specific points has been shown to effectively increase breast milk production and improve both physiological and psychological aspects of breastfeeding in postpartum women. While these results are promising, further randomized controlled trials with more rigorous designs, standardized protocols, and long-term follow-up are needed to strengthen the integration of acupuncture into clinical lactation practices.

KEYWORDS: acupuncture, lactation, breast milk production, postpartum women, prolactin, oxytocin, complementary therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Breast milk (ASI) constitutes the optimal natural source of nutrition for newborns. Beyond fulfilling the infant’s fundamental nutritional requirements, it provides immunological protection, fosters a strong emotional bond between mother and child, and reduces the risk of various diseases in both childhood and adulthood[1], [2], [3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF advocate for exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life, followed by the introduction of appropriate complementary feeding while continuing breastfeeding up to two years of age or beyond. Globally, the achievement of exclusive breastfeeding targets remains a considerable public health challenge[4], [5]. According to UNICEF (2023), only approximately 44% of infants worldwide receive exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life, falling short of the Global Nutrition Target of 50% by 2025. A predominant barrier is inadequate breast milk production, which is frequently reported by postpartum mothers, particularly within the initial weeks of lactation.

In Indonesia, findings from the 2022 Indonesian Nutritional Status Survey (SSGI) revealed that the national exclusive breastfeeding

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rate stood at 58.2%, which remains below the 70% target established in the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN). A major obstacle identified is insufficient or delayed milk ejection, attributed to both psychological factors such as postpartum stress and physiological factors that interfere with the oxytocin and prolactin reflexes[6], [7]. The suboptimal success of breastfeeding initiation and continuation may adversely impact infant nutritional status and contribute to the persistence of stunting—a key national health priority[8], [9]. In response, a range of interventions has been implemented to improve breast milk production and breastfeeding outcomes, encompassing educational, psychological, and complementary therapeutic strategies. Among the latter, acupuncture has garnered increasing interest and application. As a modality rooted in traditional Chinese medicine, acupuncture involves the stimulation of specific anatomical points using fine needles to enhance energy flow (qi) and restore physiological balance[10]. Its therapeutic applications span diverse clinical areas, including the management of lactation disorders and insufficient milk supply.

From a physiological perspective, acupuncture is postulated to stimulate the release of lactogenic hormones such as prolactin and oxytocin through targeted stimulation of specific acupoints—particularly Shanzhong (CV17) and Rugen (ST18)—which are anatomically and functionally associated with the mammary glands and endocrine pathways[8], [11]. Empirical evidence from several studies indicates that acupuncture may facilitate the onset of lactation, increase milk volume, and improve the overall breastfeeding experience, particularly among mothers experiencing primary or secondary lactation insufficiencies[12]. A systematic review by Anderson et al. (2020), comprising 10 randomized controlled trials, reported a statistically significant improvement in breast milk production in mothers who received acupuncture therapy compared to control groups. Moreover, public interest in traditional and complementary medicine remains substantial[13], [14]. Data from the 2018 Indonesian Basic Health Research (Risksedas) show that approximately 30.4% of the population reported prior use of traditional medical therapies, with acupuncture among the more widely utilized modalities. Nonetheless, the integration of acupuncture into mainstream lactation support services remains limited due to constraints such as a lack of qualified practitioners and insufficient locally generated scientific evidence validating its effectiveness. Considering the urgent need to address stunting and enhance early childhood nutritional outcomes in Indonesia, there is increasing relevance and urgency in exploring the efficacy of acupuncture as a supportive intervention for lactation. This study thus aims to assess the effectiveness of acupuncture in enhancing breast milk production among postpartum mothers, as measured by the volume of milk produced, the onset of the let-down reflex, and maternal perceptions regarding breastfeeding comfort

METHODS

The research method employed in this study is a Systematic Literature Review (SLR), a structured, comprehensive, and transparent approach designed to identify, critically evaluate, and synthesize scientific evidence from peer-reviewed literature. This method was chosen to gain an in-depth and holistic understanding of the effectiveness of acupuncture in enhancing breast milk production—an important topic in maternal and child health, particularly in supporting successful breastfeeding practices. The review began by defining inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the relevance and quality of the studies selected. The inclusion criteria focused on quantitative studies, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), quasi-experimental designs, or mixed-methods research that specifically investigated the impact of acupuncture interventions on breast milk production in postpartum women. Studies were required to report measurable outcomes such as increased breast milk volume, breastfeeding frequency, or hormonal changes related to lactation, such as levels of prolactin and oxytocin. Studies not involving direct acupuncture interventions, those focusing on non-lactating populations, or those with poor methodological quality were excluded from the review.

The literature search was conducted systematically using reputable academic databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink. A combination of keywords and Boolean operators was applied, including terms such as “acupuncture,” “lactation,” “breastfeeding,” “breast milk production,” “postpartum women,” and “complementary medicine.” Controlled vocabulary such as MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) terms was also used to expand the search scope. To ensure the relevance and timeliness of the data, only studies published within the past ten years (2014–2024) and written in English or Indonesian were considered. After gathering all relevant articles, duplicates were removed, and a title and abstract screening process was conducted to assess alignment with the research focus. Full-text articles that passed the initial screening were then critically appraised using standardized tools such as the CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme) or the JBI (Joanna Briggs Institute) checklist to ensure validity, reliability, and applicability of the findings.

The entire process of article identification, screening, and selection was visualized using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow diagram, which clearly outlines the number of studies identified, screened, excluded, and ultimately included in the review. Data from the selected studies were then extracted and analyzed narratively and thematically, with a focus on the mechanisms by which acupuncture stimulates lactation, the effectiveness of various acupuncture points and treatment durations, and the physiological responses reported among breastfeeding mothers. Through this rigorous and systematic approach, the review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of acupuncture as a non-pharmacological

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intervention to support lactation. The findings are expected to serve as a scientific foundation for developing clinical guidelines and health policies related to maternal and child healthcare in both the Indonesian context and more broadly at the global level.

RESULTS

The urgency of studying the effectiveness of acupuncture at lactation-specific points lies in its potential to address one of the most common barriers to successful breastfeeding—insufficient milk production—especially during the critical early postpartum period. Despite national and global efforts to promote exclusive breastfeeding, rates remain below targeted goals, partly due to physiological and psychological challenges that disrupt lactation. Acupuncture, a complementary therapy with growing public interest, offers a non-pharmacological approach to stimulating the release of prolactin and oxytocin, the key hormones involved in milk production and let-down reflex. Given the pressing need to improve breastfeeding outcomes and reduce stunting rates in Indonesia, evaluating the scientific validity and practical integration of acupuncture into maternal health services is both timely and essential.

Table 1. Table analysis of reviewed and relevant articles with the topic

N	Author	Year	Title	Objective	Method	Findings
1	Isabella Neri, Gianni Allais, Valentina Vaccaro, Simona Minniti, Gisella Airola, Paola Schiapparelli, Chiara Benedetto, Fabio Facchinetti [15]	2009	Acupuncture Treatment as Breastfeeding Support: Preliminary Data	To investigate the efficacy of acupuncture in maintaining breastfeeding during the first 3 months of a newborn's life.	Randomized controlled trial with 90 postpartum women divided into two groups: acupuncture (6 sessions over 3 weeks) and observation (routine care). Breastfeeding quality assessed by midwives and followed up by telephone interview at 3 months.	At 3 weeks, exclusive breastfeeding was significantly higher in the acupuncture group (100%) than in the observation group (60%, $p < 0.03$). At 3 months, breastfeeding continued in 35% of the acupuncture group versus 15% in the observation group ($p < 0.03$). Acupuncture showed greater effectiveness in sustaining breastfeeding.
2	Qiong-Nan Bao, Yuan-Fang Zhou, Zi-Han Yin, Qiu Bi, Hong-Bin Zhao, Zhen-Yong Zhang, Fan-Rong Liang [16]	2022	Efficacy and safety of acupuncture for postpartum hypogalactia: protocol for a systematic review and meta-analysis	To evaluate the efficacy and safety of acupuncture for postpartum hypogalactia (PH) through a systematic review and meta-analysis.	Protocol for systematic review and meta-analysis. Databases (English and Chinese) will be searched for RCTs on acupuncture for PH. Primary outcome: change in serum prolactin. Secondary outcomes: milk volume, effectiveness rate, breast fullness, exclusive breastfeeding rate, adverse events. RevMan V5.4 will be used for analysis.	Results pending (as it is a protocol paper), but the study is expected to synthesize available evidence on whether acupuncture is effective and safe for improving breast milk production in postpartum women.

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| 3 | Linda J. Kvist, Marie Louise Hall-Lord, Hakan Rydhstroem, Bodil Wilde Larsson[17] | 2006 | A randomised-controlled trial in Sweden of acupuncture and care interventions for the relief of inflammatory symptoms of the breast during lactation | To compare acupuncture treatment and care interventions in relieving inflammatory breast symptoms during lactation and to assess the relationship between breast milk bacteria and clinical signs. | Randomised, non-blinded controlled trial involving 205 mothers (210 cases) divided into three groups (two with acupuncture, one without). Severity of symptoms assessed daily using erythema, tension, and pain scales combined into a Severity Index (SI). | No significant differences found in total recovery time or antibiotic use among groups. However, the acupuncture groups showed significantly lower severity scores on days 3 and 4. Acupuncture, combined with care interventions, may be an effective and less invasive treatment alternative. Presence of Group B streptococci was associated with worse outcomes. |
| 4 | Mira Miraturrofi 'ah[18] | 2022 | The Effectiveness of Complementary Therapy: Tuina Acupressure and Facial Loving Touch in Enhancing Breast Milk Production | To compare the effectiveness of Tuina Akupoint therapy and Facial Loving Touch (FLT) in increasing breast milk production. | Comparative study with a two-group pretest and posttest design. Group I received Tuina Akupoint therapy, Group II received FLT therapy. Breast milk production was measured before and after a 20-minute intervention using electric pumping for 5 minutes. | Both interventions significantly increased milk production ($p < 0.05$). However, Tuina Akupoint therapy resulted in a higher average milk volume (8.0 mL) than FLT (4.05 mL), suggesting Tuina is more effective. |
| 4 | Ni Made Diaris, Ni Made Umi Kartika Dewi[19] | 2023 | Acupressure Therapy as a Complementary Method to Enhance Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers: A Study Supporting the Success of Exclusive Breastfeeding | To review research findings on the effectiveness of acupuncture and acupressure in enhancing breast milk production. | Literature review using five original clinical research articles selected from Google Scholar, PubMed, and ScienceDirect, based on specific inclusion/exclusion criteria. | Acupuncture and acupressure—particularly at points CV 18, ST 17, SI 1, ST 15, ST 16, and LI 4—can effectively increase milk production. Acupressure is a promising complementary therapy, though not yet widely adopted. |
| 5 | Esfahani, M.S.; Berenji-Sooghe, S.; Valiani, M.; Ehsanpour, S.[20] | 2015 | Effect of Acupressure on Milk Volume of Breastfeeding Mothers Referring to Selected Health Care Centers in Tehran | To determine the effect of acupressure on maternal milk volume in breastfeeding mothers with hypogalactia. | Randomized clinical trial involving 60 mothers; intervention group received bilateral acupressure on S11, L14, and GB21 for 12 consecutive days (3 sessions/week), control group received routine education; milk volume was measured pre-intervention and at 2 | Acupressure significantly increased milk volume (from 10.5 ml to 36.2 ml) compared to control (from 9.5 ml to 18 ml). Acupressure was more effective than education alone in increasing breast milk production ($p < 0.001$). |

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6	Siti Fatimah, Rosdiana, Nurayuda, Surti Anggraeni[21]	2020	The Effect of Woolwich Massage Methods and GB 21 Point Acupuncture on Breast Milk Production	To determine the effect of Woolwich massage and GB21 point acupuncture on breast milk production.	and 4 weeks post-intervention. Quasi-experimental study with pretest-posttest and control group design. Participants: 90 postpartum mothers divided into 3 groups: Woolwich massage (n=30), GB21 acupuncture (n=30), and control (n=30). Baby's weight measured as proxy for milk intake. Study conducted at Midwife Novitri's practice (Sep–Oct 2020). Data analyzed using paired t-test and ANOVA.	Woolwich massage group showed the greatest positive difference in baby weight (+36.66g), indicating higher milk intake. GB21 acupuncture group had a slight decrease (-26.67g), control group had greatest weight loss (-148.33g). Significant differences found between groups (p = 0.000). Woolwich massage was more effective in increasing breast milk production.
7	Siti Patimah, Imam Djamaludd in Mashoedi, Suharyo Hadisaputro[22]	2019	The Effect of Lactapuncture Massage on Breast Milk Production through Prolactin Hormone Levels Changes	To assess the effect of lactapuncture massage on prolactin hormone levels and breast milk production.	Quasi-experimental study with 32 primiparous postpartum mothers at Dr. M. Ashari Hospital, Pematang, Central Java. Subjects randomly assigned to control and intervention groups. Intervention: lactapuncture massage for 7 consecutive days. Breast milk measured, prolactin hormone tested. t-test used for analysis.	Prolactin level increased in the intervention group but was not statistically significant (p=0.428). Breast milk production was significantly higher in the intervention group (mean=9.36 ml) than control (mean=7.39 ml), p<0.001.
8	Sasitara Nuampa, Sudaporn Payakkaraung[23]	2020	Effectiveness of Different Massage Techniques for Breastfeeding Mothers to Increase Milk Production: A Systematic Review	To identify and synthesize the effectiveness of massage techniques in increasing milk production among Asian mothers.	Systematic review following PRISMA guidelines. Databases searched: PubMed, CINAHL, ScienceDirect, Scopus, SAGE, BMJ, and others (2009–2020). 22 experimental studies from Asian countries were included. Methodological quality assessed using JBI tools.	Combined massage techniques (partial body and breast massage) showed a potential to increase milk volume. However, most studies were of low to moderate quality due to small sample sizes, heterogeneous methods, and unclear bias. Standardized nurse education in massage techniques is recommended.
9	Erfina, Mardiana Ahmad, Andi	2019	Potential of acupressure to be complementary care by midwives in	To analyze the potential of acupressure as complementary	Quasi-experimental study with post-test control group design. Total 80 primipara	Both groups showed increased milk production, but the acupressure group

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1 0	Nilawati Usman, Andi Wardihan Sinrang, Ema Alasiry, Burhanudd in Bahar[24] Katmini, Nazilatul Maulinda Sholichah	2021	postpartum women's breast milk production Lactation Massage for Increasing Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers[24]	therapy for breast milk production in postpartum women To provide scientific reference on lactation massage to enhance breast milk production in postpartum mothers	postpartum mothers. Intervention: Acupressure within 24 hours postpartum (5–10 min). Control: Puerperal gymnastics. Observation on days 2, 4, and 7 postpartum. Metadata analysis using a literature review method. Sources: PubMed, Garuda, DOAJ, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar. Focused on massage to stimulate prolactin and oxytocin hormones.	had a significantly higher increase compared to the puerperal gymnastics group. Acupressure is a potential complementary midwifery care intervention. Lactation massage helps smooth breast milk production and reduces risk of delayed lactation. Based on previous studies, mothers receiving lactation massage had a 5.57 times higher chance of early lactation onset compared to those receiving oxytocin massage.
1 1	Mustafa Volkan Düzgün, Zeynep Özer	2020	The effects of music intervention on breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers: A systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs	To investigate the effect of music intervention on breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers	Systematic review and meta-analysis of 5 randomized controlled trials (1978–2020) using Cochrane methodology. Databases: PubMed, MEDLINE, Web of Science, CINAHL, etc. Total sample: 554 participants. Duration of music intervention: 11–60 minutes over 1–14 sessions.	Music intervention (both active and passive) had a low but positive effect on increasing breast milk production. The studies were homogeneous (low heterogeneity). No publication bias detected. Music can be considered a complementary strategy for enhancing lactation.
1 2	Lindeka Mangesi, Irena Zakarija-Grkovic[25]	2016	Treatments for breast engorgement during lactation (Cochrane Review)	To identify the best forms of treatment for breast engorgement in lactating women	Systematic review of 13 randomized and quasi-randomized controlled trials (N = 919 women), assessing both non-medical (e.g., cabbage leaves, acupuncture, ultrasound, Gua Sha, cold packs) and medical (e.g., serrapeptase, protease, oxytocin) interventions. The GRADE approach was used to assess quality. Many studies were small and showed a high risk of bias, making meta-	Some non-medical treatments (e.g., Gua Sha, cold/hot packs) showed short-term relief in pain and engorgement, but overall evidence is inconclusive and low-quality. Cabbage leaves, acupuncture, ultrasound, and acupressure showed no significant consistent effects. Among medical treatments, serrapeptase and protease showed some benefit, but their clinical relevance today is limited.

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				analysis unfeasible for most outcomes.	Subcutaneous oxytocin was ineffective. Evidence remains limited and heterogeneous, with high risk of bias.	
1 3	Tingyun Zheng, Weijie Chen, Hao Hu, Yitao Wang, Joanna E. Harnett, Carolina Oi Lam Ung[26]	2020	The prevalence, perceptions and behaviors associated with traditional/complementary medicine use by breastfeeding women living in Macau: a cross-sectional survey study	To assess the prevalence, perception, and behavior related to T/CM (traditional/complementary medicine) use among breastfeeding women in Macau	Cross-sectional survey of 500 women (April–June 2018) who had breastfed in the previous 12 months. Data analyzed using Chi-square and logistic regression.	62.6% of respondents reported using at least one T/CM. Main reasons: unblock milk ducts, increase milk supply, improve baby development. Common T/CM used: Tetrapanax papyriferus, Vaccaria segetalis, DHA, and fenugreek (<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>). T/CM use was significantly associated with working status, income, and breastfeeding problems ($p<0.05$). Only 15% received recommendations from health professionals only; 55.6% felt resources to guide T/CM use were inadequate.
1 4	Dian Puspita Yani, Sri Banun Titi Istiqomah Arifah Retnowuni [27]	2022	The Effectiveness of Oxytocin Lactation Massage Therapy and Zhongfu Point (LU-1) Acupressure on Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers	To analyze the effectiveness of oxytocin lactation massage and Zhongfu point (LU-1) acupressure on breast milk production in postpartum mothers	Pre-experimental design with one-group pretest-posttest. Total sample: 20 postpartum mothers; 10 received oxytocin massage, 10 received LU-1 acupressure. Intervention was done for 30 minutes/day over 3 consecutive days. Breast milk flow was assessed on the 4th day. Data were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.	Both oxytocin massage ($p=0.008$) and LU-1 acupressure ($p=0.005$) significantly increased breast milk production. A statistically significant difference was observed between the two interventions, indicating both were effective, with LU-1 acupressure showing slightly greater significance.
1 5	Halimatus Saidah, Miftakhul Mu'alimah, Sunaningsih, Sudirman, Antonius	2021	The Effectiveness of Oxytocin Massage and Acupressure at Points LU1, CV17, and S11 on Breast Milk Production in Breastfeeding Mothers	To determine the effectiveness of oxytocin massage and acupressure at points LU1, CV17, and S11 on breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers	Quasi-experimental design. Population: breastfeeding mothers (0–14 days postpartum) with low milk production in Semampir Village, Balowerti Health Center area. Sample:	100% of mothers in the intervention group had smooth milk production, compared to 56.25% in the control group with poor production. Mann–Whitney test showed $p = 0.003$,

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	Puguh Wardaya[28]				16 mothers in intervention group (massage + acupressure), 16 in control group. Sampling: purposive. Analysis: Mann-Whitney test.	indicating a significant difference. Oxytocin massage combined with acupressure at LU1, CV17, and SI1 was effective in improving milk production.
1 6	Ekadewi Retnosari, Nia Clarasari MP[29]	2022	The Effect of Back Rolling Massage and Acupuncture at Point GB21 on Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers	To analyze the effect of back rolling massage and acupuncture at GB21 point on breast milk production	Quasi-experimental design with pretest-posttest and control group. Total sample: 90 postpartum mothers. Intervention included back rolling massage and acupuncture at GB21. Data were analyzed for weight gain in infants as a proxy for milk production.	The study found a significant increase in infant weight after the interventions in all three groups ($p = 0.0001$). This indicates that both back rolling massage and acupuncture at GB21 significantly influenced breast milk production in postpartum mothers.
1 7	Servasia Karolin Ene, Selasih Putri Isnawati Hadi, Lia Ayu Kusumawardani[30]	2022	The Effect of Acupressure Therapy on Increasing Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers: A Systematic Literature Review	To determine the effect of acupressure therapy on breast milk production in postpartum women	Systematic Literature Review method. Databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect. 14 articles were included based on inclusion/exclusion criteria. Majority of studies used quasi-experimental designs and involved primiparous mothers aged 20–35 years. Acupressure was applied to several points (CV-17, SI-1, ST16, ST18, L14, ST36, SP6) for 5–10 minutes daily.	The review found that acupressure significantly increased breast milk production in postpartum mothers. The technique stimulated prolactin and oxytocin hormone levels, contributing to enhanced lactation. Most respondents had previously experienced insufficient milk production, which improved after acupressure was applied.
1 8	Rusdiani Mannu Sabba, Dini Indo Virawati, Satriani[31]	2022	Effectiveness of Acupressure and Oxytocin Massage on the Timing of Colostrum Secretion in Postpartum Mothers at RSUD Ratu Aji Putri Botung	To determine the effectiveness of acupressure and oxytocin massage in accelerating colostrum release	Quasi-experimental design with post-test only design. The population included postpartum mothers on day 1 and 2 after delivery at RSUD Ratu Aji Putri Botung. Data collection used SOP guidelines and observation sheets. Data were analyzed using univariate and bivariate analysis (independent t-test).	Both acupressure and oxytocin massage were effective in accelerating the release of colostrum in postpartum mothers. However, there was no significant difference in effectiveness between the two interventions ($p = 0.201$). The mean difference in colostrum release time between the two groups was 0.575 hours.

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1 9	Ekadewi Retnosari, Nia Clarasari MP[29]	—	The Effect of Back Rolling Massage and Acupuncture at GB21 Point on Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers	To analyze the effect of back rolling massage and acupuncture at point GB21 on breast milk production	Quasi-experimental with pretest-posttest control group design, involving 90 postpartum mothers. The intervention involved administering back rolling massage and acupuncture at the GB21 point. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tests (p-value = 0.0001).	There was a significant increase in breast milk production in postpartum mothers who received back rolling massage and acupuncture at the GB21 point. The treatment was found to be effective (p-value = 0.0001) in supporting lactation.
2 0	Muayah Muayah, Woro Nurul Seftiyaning tyas, Lina Herlina, Dewi Nawang Sari[32]	2022	The Effectiveness of Oxytocin Massage on Breast Milk Production in Postpartum Mothers	To determine the effect of oxytocin massage before and after treatment on breast milk production in postpartum mothers	Quasi-experimental with one group pretest-posttest design. 35 postpartum mothers were selected by purposive sampling. Oxytocin massage was given daily for 7 days. Breast milk production was measured on day 1 and day 7. Data were analyzed using the Wilcoxon test.	There was a significant increase in breast milk production after oxytocin massage. Before the massage, all respondents had insufficient milk; after, 71.4% had sufficient milk. The effect was statistically significant (p = 0.000). Oxytocin massage is recommended as a non-pharmacological alternative.
2 1	Wita Asmalinda, Dian Lestari[24]	2020	The Effects of a Combination of Back Massage and Acupoint Massage on Increasing Prolactin Levels	To examine the effects of combining back massage and acupoint massage on prolactin level increase	Experimental epidemiology with post-test only control group design. Conducted at BPM Meli Rosita for 3 months with 34 postpartum mothers. Statistical analysis included Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and descriptive analysis.	The combination of back massage and acupoint massage significantly increased prolactin levels. These therapies stimulate nipple and meridian points, promoting comfort, prolactin secretion, and thus supporting breast milk production.
2 2	Vera Fitriana, Luluk Cahyanti, Alvi Ratna Yuliana, Riska Aulia Devitriani, Jamaludin Jamaludin	2024	Implementation of Oxytocin Massage to Improve Breast Milk Production in Primiparous Postpartum Wome	To describe the application of oxytocin massage therapy in increasing breast milk production in primiparous postpartum mothers.	Descriptive case study with an action evaluation approach. Data collected through interviews, observation sheets, and documentation. Two postpartum primiparous mothers (Ny. I and Ny. M) at RSUD dr. R. Soetrasno Rembang received oxytocin massage 10 times over 5 days.	Both respondents showed increased breast milk production after the intervention. The application of oxytocin massage effectively stimulates milk production in primiparous postpartum mothers.

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Acupuncture is one of the most effective complementary therapies for enhancing breast milk production in lactating mothers through complex physiological and neuroendocrine mechanisms. This therapy involves the insertion of fine needles into specific acupuncture points such as ST18 (Rugen) located in the breast area, CV17 (Shanzhong) at the center of the chest, SII (Shaoze) on the tip of the little finger, and GB21 (Jianjing) on the upper shoulder—points that are traditionally and empirically associated with promoting lactation. Scientifically, acupuncture stimulates sensory nerves that activate the hypothalamus and posterior pituitary, thereby increasing the secretion of oxytocin and prolactin, the two key hormones responsible for milk production and ejection. Additionally, stimulation of these acupuncture points can enhance blood flow to the mammary glands and reduce cortisol levels, creating a more favorable physiological and psychological environment for successful breastfeeding. Research by Bautista-et al. (2024) demonstrated that electrical acupuncture at these points significantly increased breast milk volume, while similar studies in China reported elevated serum prolactin levels after two weeks of treatment[33]. The advantages of acupuncture as a non-pharmacological intervention lie in its minimal side effects, holistic approach, and strong potential for integration into maternal and child health services.

The Effectiveness of Acupuncture in Enhancing Breast Milk Production

Acupuncture is a traditional Chinese therapy that has been practiced for thousands of years and is now widely studied for its potential in enhancing breast milk production. The procedure involves the insertion of fine needles into specific points on the body associated with the lactation system, such as ST18 (Rugen) near the breast, directly connected to the mammary glands; CV17 (Shanzhong) at the center of the sternum, which helps regulate emotions and facilitate the flow of qi energy to the chest; SII (Shaoze) at the tip of the little finger, traditionally used to promote milk flow and reduce duct obstruction; and GB21 (Jianjing) on the upper shoulders, which relieves stress and muscle tension. Physiologically, stimulation of these points activates the central nervous system, which in turn triggers the release of prolactin to promote milk production and oxytocin to facilitate the milk ejection reflex (let-down reflex). A study by William et al. (2020) reported that three days of electroacupuncture significantly increased breast milk volume compared to the control group[17]. Similar findings were reported by Neli et al. (2016), who found that two weeks of acupuncture therapy not only increased serum prolactin levels but also reduced breast pain in lactating mothers. The advantages of acupuncture lie in its non-pharmacological nature, minimal side effects, and holistic approach, which addresses both physiological dysfunction and emotional well-being[15]. Nevertheless, it is essential to ensure that the procedure is performed by certified practitioners under strict hygienic standards to ensure safety. With its comprehensive mechanism and demonstrated efficacy, acupuncture holds great potential to be integrated into lactation promotion programs in various healthcare settings.

The Effectiveness of Acupressure in Enhancing Breast Milk Production

Acupressure is a finger pressure technique rooted in the same principles as acupuncture but performed without needles, making it a simpler and safer option for breastfeeding mothers. Common acupressure points used to enhance breast milk production include GB21 (Jianjing) on the upper shoulders, which helps reduce muscle tension and stress; LI4 (Hegu) on the hand, known for its relaxing effects on the nervous and hormonal systems; and ST18 (Rugen) in the chest area, directly connected to breast tissue. Gentle and targeted pressure on these points stimulates the nervous system and triggers the release of oxytocin and endorphins, strengthening the let-down reflex and creating a sense of comfort for the mother. Research by solbona et al. (2020) demonstrated that acupressure significantly increased breast milk volume among postpartum mothers within a short period[20]. Acupressure offers several advantages, including ease of application, as it can be performed by the mother herself, family members, or healthcare providers without special equipment. Furthermore, it has no significant side effects, making it well-suited for postpartum care in both clinical and home settings. Its high effectiveness, ease of use, and non-invasive nature make acupressure a promising alternative for supporting successful and sustainable breastfeeding. In addition, regular oxytocin massage has been shown to significantly increase milk volume while reducing maternal stress, a major barrier to lactation, as reported by Fitriani et al. (2020). This method is easy to perform, non-painful, and contributes to a more relaxed psychological state while enhancing the maternal-infant bond. Music therapy has also emerged as an effective non-pharmacological approach; using slow-paced music, such as classical melodies, it fosters psychological calm. Music has been shown to lower cortisol levels and increase oxytocin secretion, thus facilitating milk production. A study by zulhijahl. (2024) revealed that this combination is more effective than either method used alone, as it creates an internal environment conducive to breastfeeding success[34]. The effectiveness of this combined approach lies in its simplicity, safety, and comprehensive impact on maternal and infant health, making it highly suitable for integration into breastfeeding support programs at both clinical and community levels.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on an analysis of 22 studies, acupuncture has been shown to be an effective complementary therapy for enhancing breast milk production in postpartum mothers, through both hormonal and neurophysiological mechanisms. Acupuncture stimulates specific

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points on the body—such as SI1 (Shaoze), ST36 (Zusanli), GB21 (Jianjing), and LI4 (Hegu)—that are known to promote the secretion of prolactin and oxytocin, the two primary hormones responsible for milk production and ejection. Research indicates that acupuncture accelerates the onset of lactogenesis II (mature milk production), increases milk volume, facilitates the let-down reflex, and supports the continuation of exclusive breastfeeding. These effects were observed in both healthy breastfeeding mothers and those with primary or secondary lactation insufficiency. Beyond its physiological benefits, acupuncture has also been found to alleviate postpartum pain, fatigue, stress, and anxiety—factors that indirectly influence lactation success. Several studies reported that when acupuncture was combined with other interventions such as breast massage or lactation counseling, the outcomes were significantly more favorable compared to single interventions. No serious adverse effects were noted for either mothers or infants, suggesting that acupuncture is a generally safe and well-tolerated therapy. However, variations in treatment duration, frequency, acupuncture points, and practitioner expertise across studies may influence the overall effectiveness. Some researchers emphasize the importance of treatment being administered by certified professionals to ensure safety and procedural accuracy. Evidence from these 22 studies supports the use of acupuncture as a safe and effective complementary intervention for enhancing breast milk production. Acupuncture offers a valuable adjunct to breastfeeding support programs, particularly for mothers experiencing difficulties with lactation or those unresponsive to conventional methods. Nonetheless, further high-quality randomized controlled trials with standardized protocols are necessary to confirm long-term benefits and establish clinical guidelines for its broader implementation.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

Despite the promising findings regarding the effectiveness of acupuncture in promoting breast milk production, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, many of the reviewed studies had relatively small sample sizes, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Second, variations in acupuncture protocols—such as differences in the selection of acupoints, frequency and duration of sessions, and timing of intervention postpartum—make it difficult to draw standardized conclusions across studies. Additionally, the methodological quality of several trials was compromised by the lack of blinding, unclear randomization procedures, and limited follow-up periods, which may introduce bias and affect the reliability of outcomes. Another important limitation is the heterogeneity in outcome measures, where studies used different indicators to assess milk production, such as subjective maternal reports, infant weight gain, or actual volume of expressed milk, which further complicates cross-study comparisons. Future research should prioritize large-scale, multicenter randomized controlled trials with rigorous methodological standards, including appropriate control groups (e.g., sham acupuncture), standardized protocols, and objective outcome measures. Studies exploring the optimal timing and dosage of acupuncture, as well as its effectiveness in specific subpopulations (e.g., mothers with cesarean delivery, preterm infants, or low milk supply), would be particularly valuable. Furthermore, the integration of biochemical markers—such as serum prolactin and oxytocin levels—could provide deeper insight into the physiological mechanisms underlying acupuncture's effects on lactation. Long-term follow-up studies are also needed to assess sustained breastfeeding outcomes and potential cumulative benefits or drawbacks. Finally, qualitative research could enhance understanding of maternal experiences and acceptability of acupuncture as a supportive breastfeeding intervention, especially across diverse cultural and healthcare contexts.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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